

WOMEN, INSTITUTIONAL, AND INFORMAL REFORMS UNDER KING SALMAN IN SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract

Women's involvement in many aspects of society (government, administration, law, diplomacy) has been facilitated by both formal and informal means of reform associated with the government's Vision 2030 programme, as well as through legislation that allows women to participate more actively in society. However, while such policies have been successful in providing women with greater access and an increasing number of opportunities to participate as equal citizens, access continues to be limited and is heavily influenced by existing socio-political and economic constraints. This study examines the impact of the above-mentioned changes on women's ability to engage politically and socially in a country that has long been known for its restrictive political climate and to provide insight into the future development of women in Saudi Arabia based on an assessment of the existing political system in conjunction with analysis of civil society, private sector, and other informal mechanisms for engagement. This paper furthers the scholarship on the gender-related Middle East studies by displaying how state-based reform efforts can promote women's inclusion while retaining authority over politics and provide insight into the limitations and potential of "reform-based" empowerment attempts. The research incorporates a qualitative research approach primarily via the secondary data analysis method. A collection of sources, including official government reports, official policies and statistical information, peer-reviewed academic literature, global indexing metrics, and reliable media outlets, is reviewed to identify women's institutional and non-institutional (informal) involvement during the reign of King Salman. The paper seeks to analyse the impact of reforms on women's government involvement and determine if/how informal spaces and digital spaces were used to enhance women's participation. Secondly, the research seeks to offer a balanced picture of Prospects, barriers and challenges of women becoming empowered.

Key Words: *Women, Vision 2023, King Salman, Reforms, empowerment*

1. INTRODUCTION

With the leadership of King Salman, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia continues the tradition of increasing women's roles in politics. This represents a major change in a culture where, historically, women did not have access to decision-making in the areas of public and political life. As part of this transformation, women's involvement in politics is closely associated with the overall goal of implementing a broad reform agenda that aligns with the Kingdom's Vision 2030 initiative. The Vision 2030 initiative seeks to advance modernization of state institutions, promote economic diversity, and facilitate the inclusion of all segments of society by improving their access to economic opportunity. As part of this initiative, women's participation in politics has become both a goal for development and a symbolic measure of the successful implementation of the overall Reform Agenda, representing the Kingdom's desire for modernization while maintaining its tradition of political continuity. Under King Salman, women's increased participation in the political arena has allowed them to expand their previous levels of participation in both formal and informal politics. As far as formal political participation is concerned, appointments to positions of advisory and executive nature provided women with an opportunity to gain visibility and representation within political structures. Additionally, during the reign of King Salman, women were appointed to leadership roles in various sectors; this demonstrates a shift from earlier practices, which largely restricted women's access to social and charitable functions.

Women as deputy ministers, ambassadors, and Shura Council delegates provide advice and recommendations on policies pertaining to education, health, labour and social development and economic reform. They are appointed to these positions by the Government, demonstrating a commitment by the Government to include women in the governance structure without changing the existing political system in Saudi Arabia, which is highly centralised. The Shura Council, though only providing recommendations to the King, has become an essential tool for women to become involved in politics. Women's representation and leadership in the council demonstrates an evolution from token representation to active participation in discussions and working with committees, and developing policies. Additionally, the appointment of women to senior roles within the ministries and national authorities shows a commitment by the State to increase the number of women who are involved in the administration of the public service and implement policy. Furthermore, the appointment of female ambassadors in international relations has

expanded the role of women in Saudi Arabia by providing opportunities for women to represent their countries on a global level, thereby contributing to the body of diplomatic work.

As part of an ongoing trend established during King Salman's reign, women's involvement in politics has expanded through informal and alternative avenues. Digital governance tools, social media, civil society groups, and public consultation processes are prominent ways that women have used to share their views, advocate for change, and communicate with decision-makers. Given that electoral participation and legislative authority remain relatively weak in a repressive system, these informal methods represent a significant way for women to influence overall political discussion and to affect outcomes at the level of public policy. Women have created new ways of interacting with and shaping legislation through the use of e-petitions, e-participation forums, and civic action groups. Strengthening the role of women via social and legal reform initiatives, such as removing the need for women to have a male guardian in order to travel and providing mechanisms that facilitate independent travel for women, has enabled women to take part in public life through increased access to various levels of education, employment, and political involvement. The reforms that have taken place do not lead to complete political equality, but they provide the starting point for increased female involvement in both governance and society. Overall, under King Salman, Women's participation in the political system follows an incremental and controlled approach to reform. Institutional participation, legal reform, and informal participation channels have all been created to expand the role of Women in Saudi Arabia, but all continue to function within the confines of the centralized, monarchical political system. The analysis of these informal and institutional reforms allows us to gain insight into how women's political empowerment and inclusion are evolving in present-day Saudi Arabia.

2. SHURA COUNCIL AND SAUDI WOMEN

Under King Salman, women's role in the **Shura Council** (Consultative Assembly) has not only been maintained but also gradually expanded, reflecting the broader social reforms associated with *Vision 2030*. The King has realised the significance of women's participation the council in shaping advisory opinions on issues such as education, health, family affairs, and economic, social and other reforms. A major milestone came in **2020**, when **Dr. Hanan Al-Ahmadi** became the **first woman appointed Assistant Speaker of the Shura Council**, and later the first woman to **chair a Council session**. This marked a symbolic shift, highlighting women's ability to occupy

leadership roles within Saudi Arabia's political institutions. More recently, in 2024, the quota was reinforced again, with **19 women appointed to the newly formed Council**, keeping female representation at around 20%.¹ Newly appointed female members of the council come from diverse professional backgrounds. Prominent appointees include Dr. Arwa Al Rashid, Dr. Ishraq Rafaei, Dr. Amal Qattan, and Dr. Taqwa Omar. Their expertise is expected to add value to the council's discussions. The list also includes returning members like Dr. Asma Al Muwaisher and Princess Dr. Al Jawhara Al Saud. These experienced figures will continue to make significant contributions to the council's work.² Although the Shura Council remains an advisory body without legislative power, women's growing visibility and leadership within it demonstrates gradual but meaningful political inclusion. Their role has shifted from symbolic presence to active participation in debates and committees, signaling an incremental increase in women's influence within Saudi governance under King Salman. Women's political participation has extended beyond the **Shura Council** into broader governance and state institutions, though still within limits defined by the monarchy. Their inclusion in senior positions reflects part of the Kingdom's **Vision 2030 reforms**, aimed at empowering women in public life. They have also served as deputy ministers and high-ranking officials in ministries such as education, labour, and health.

Tamadur bint Youssef Al-Ramah was appointed as **Deputy Minister of Labour and Social Development** in 2018, making her one of the most senior female officials in the Kingdom. And Sarah-Al Suhaimi became the first woman to chair Saudi Arabia's stock exchange.³ In 2022, King Salman appointed Shihana Alazzaz as the Deputy Secretary-General of the Council of Ministers. She is a pioneering woman lawyer, previously General Counsel at the Public Investment Fund. Her involvement as the secretary is creating a good impact in the Saudi political environment.⁴ Princess Haifa bint Mohammed Al Saud, appointed in 2022 as **Deputy Minister of Tourism for**

¹ Khitam Al Amir, "19 More Women Join Saudi Shura Council, Female Representation Reaches 20%," *Gulf News*, September 3, 2024, <https://gulfnews.com/world/gulf/saudi/19-more-women-join-saudi-shura-council-female-representation-reaches-20-1.1725357429952>

² Ibid.

³ Sushmita Roy, "Saudi Arabia Just Appointed Its First Female Ambassador to the US," *Global Citizen*, February 25, 2019, <https://www.globalcitizen.org/en/content/saudi-arabia-first-female-ambassador-to-the-us/>

⁴ Khitam Al Amir, "19 More Women Join Saudi Shura Council, Female Representation Reaches 20%," *Gulf News*, December 3, 2022, <https://www.arabnews.com/node/2115711/saudi-arabia?>

Strategy and Investment, also serves as **Vice Chairperson of the Saudi Fencing Federation** and heads the **Women’s Committee at the Arab Fencing Federation**. She is a board member of both the **Al-Ahsa and Taif Development Authorities**.⁵ **Deemah Al-Yahya**, a digital economy expert, became **Secretary-General of the Digital Cooperation Organisation in 2021**, the first Saudi woman to lead an international intergovernmental body.⁶

Similarly, women have been appointed to roles such as undersecretaries and secretaries-general in ministries dealing with social, cultural, and economic affairs. Although the Shura Council is advisory in nature, women’s active engagement demonstrates their growing role in shaping national dialogue. Women have been given leadership positions in national councils and authorities, such as the Human Rights Commission, the Saudi Sports Authority, and various cultural institutions. These appointments align with the state’s push to increase women’s visibility in governance.

3. THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN MUNICIPAL COUNCIL

Under King Salman bin Abdulaziz Al Saud, Saudi Arabia’s municipal councils have seen only limited changes, especially when it comes to women’s participation. In **2015**, for the first time, women were allowed to vote and run for office in municipal elections. Around **20 women were elected** out of more than **2,000 seats**, and some were also appointed by royal decree to encourage their involvement.⁷ This marked an important step in expanding women’s roles in public life. Since then, however, no further municipal elections have been held, and women’s representation has not increased.⁸ Women who were part of the councils mostly worked in advisory roles or in local development services like health, education, and urban planning. Their participation reflected broader reforms under **Vision 2030**, aiming to involve women more in public affairs, but these

⁵ Saudipedia, “Haifa Bint Mohammed Al Saud,” accessed October 19, 2025, <https://saudipedia.com/en/article/4029/figures/officials/haifa-bint-mohammed-al-saud#:~:text=Princess%20Haifa%20Bint%20Mohammed%20Bin,at%20the%20Arab%20Fencing%20Federation>

⁶ Deemah AlYahya, "Deemah AlYahya," *Digital Cooperation Organization*, accessed October 19, 2025, <https://dco.org/secretariat/deemah-alyahya/>.

⁷ Sushmita Roy, “Saudi Arabia Just Appointed Its First Female Ambassador to the US,” *Global Citizen*, February 25, 2019, <https://www.globalcitizen.org/en/content/saudi-arabia-first-female-ambassador-to-the-us/>

⁸ Ibid.

councils themselves had limited decision-making powers and mainly acted as advisors to local officials.

The municipal councils' term was extended until **2021**, but after that, they were dissolved, and no new elections have taken place³. The lack of transparency in how the councils functioned led to criticism from citizens, who demanded better oversight and clearer reporting on projects. As a result, by **2025**, there will be no women serving as municipal councillors, and the number is likely to remain very limited.⁹

While women's participation in governance was seen as a step forward, the absence of regular elections and the limited powers of the councils have prevented this progress from continuing. The reforms introduced by King Salman have helped open doors for women in other areas, but in local governance, the progress has stalled, highlighting the need for further steps to strengthen their role in decision-making.

4. THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN FOREIGN POLICY

Saudi women's role in foreign diplomacy has significantly increased under Vision 2030 reforms, with women serving as ambassadors and in other diplomatic roles on the global stage. Events like the International Day of Women in Diplomacy highlight these advancements. Historically excluded from diplomatic service, women have now been entrusted with key roles representing the Kingdom abroad, marking a significant shift in gender inclusion in state affairs. Saudi women now serve as ambassadors, leaders in international organizations, and members of foreign missions and delegations.¹⁰ **Princess Reema bint Bandar Al Saud** is the most prominent example. In **2019**, she was appointed **Saudi Arabia's first female ambassador**, representing the Kingdom in the **United States** with ministerial rank.¹¹ Her appointment was a groundbreaking step that signaled the Kingdom's willingness to incorporate women into high-level diplomatic roles.

⁹ Hanaa Faize A. Moubarak and Asyraf Afthanorhan, "Psychological Empowerment of Politically Empowered Saudi Women," *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 12, no. 517 (2025): <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-04610-8>

¹⁰ Einas Al-Shahwan, "Saudi Arabia Appoints Third Female Ambassador," *Asharq Al-Awsat*, April 22, 2021, <https://english.aawsat.com/home/article/2933061/saudi-arabia-appoints-third-female-ambassador>

¹¹ Reema bint Bandar bin Sultan bin Abdulaziz Al Saud, "Reema Bint Bandar bin Sultan bin Abdulaz," *Chicago Council on Global Affairs*, accessed October 19, 2025, <https://globalaffairs.org/research/experts/reema-bint-bandar-bin-sultan-bin-abdulaz>

Saudi Arabia recently appointed Inas Al-Shahwan as its ambassador to Sweden and Iceland, making her the third female diplomat from the Kingdom after Princess Reema bint Bandar and Amal Al-Mouallimi.¹² This milestone highlights the growing role of women in representing Saudi interests abroad and shaping the nation's diplomatic relations.

In January 2023, the Kingdom expanded women's participation in foreign affairs by appointing Haifa al-Jadea as Ambassador to the European Union and EAEC, and Nisreen bint Hamad al-Shibel as Ambassador to Finland. Additionally, Princess Haifa bint Abdulaziz Al-Mogrin, who formerly served as Saudi Arabia's Permanent Delegate to UNESCO, was assigned as Ambassador to Spain.¹³ These appointments mark a significant step toward enhancing women's presence in global diplomatic circles.

On International Women's Day in 2024, Saudi Arabia celebrated six female ambassadors actively contributing to the country's international diplomacy under the Vision 2030 reforms. These leaders, including Princess Haifa Al-Mogrin, Princess Reema Al Saud, Haifa Al Jedea, Amal Al Moallimi, Enas Al-Shahwan, and Nisreen Al Shibel, hold advanced educational qualifications and have been influential in areas like development and cooperation.¹⁴ Their roles reflect the Kingdom's dedication to advancing women's leadership and participation in global governance.

In addition to this historic post, women are increasingly involved in diplomatic forums, international conferences, and cross-border cooperation initiatives, often serving as advisors, delegates, or representatives in multilateral bodies. Their presence supports the Kingdom's efforts to diversify its diplomatic outreach and portray a modern image aligned with global economic, cultural, and technological partnerships. While their roles remain limited compared to their male counterparts, these appointments reflect deliberate policy shifts aimed at expanding women's participation in governance and international relations.

However, Saudi women's involvement in foreign diplomacy is still in its early stages and the king has around 4% share of women ambassadors according to 2024 data and this percentage is

¹² Ibid.

¹³ "Who's Who: Princess Haifa Al-Mogrin, Saudi ambassador to Spain". *Arab News*. 3 January 2024. Retrieved 13 July 2025.

¹⁴ <https://www.harpersbazaararabia.com/culture/people/international-womens-day-meet-6-saudi-female-ambassadors-and-dignitaries-representing-the-kingdom>

considered very low, but women's significance and the current policy of the government increase hope to expand women's role in foreign affairs.

Figure

Source: Anwar Gargash Diplomatic Academy (AGDA), *2023/2024 Women in Diplomacy Index*, authored by Dr. Sara Chehab, Senior Research Fellow, AGDA Insight Programme, 2023/2024 report.

According to a 2024 report, the MENA region had 10% share of women ambassadors, indicating a relatively lower representation of women in ambassadorial roles compared to the global average of 21%. The GCC region holds a smaller share at 5.6%, reflecting limited progress in gender inclusion within diplomatic positions. Within the GCC, Saudi Arabia's share stands at 4%, highlighting that although it is making strides under initiatives like Vision 2030, there is still significant room for improvement. This distribution underscores ongoing gender disparities in diplomatic representation and the need for continued efforts to empower women across the region. In recent years, Saudi women have increasingly assumed leadership roles in international organisations, reflecting broader social and political reforms under Vision 2030. Now, women serve in key roles within organisations such as **UNESCO**, the **European Union**, and Human

Rights Organisation and so on.¹⁵ Their involvement in global forums underscores Saudi Arabia's evolving stance on women's leadership and its readiness to contribute to international dialogue on education, human rights, environmental issues, and economic cooperation.

5. WOMEN AND DIGITAL AND E-PARTICIPATION

Women's participation in e-governance in Saudi Arabia has emerged as a significant form of political involvement, particularly under the reforms of Vision 2030, which aims to modernize government interaction through technology. Women are increasingly using digital platforms to share their views and influence public policies, especially in areas such as education, healthcare, and family welfare. Online petitions have become a popular method for women to collectively advocate for change and ensure that their concerns reach decision-makers. These digital tools provide a structured and accessible way to engage in politics, especially for those who may not have access to formal political forums.

The rise of social media platforms has played a crucial role in expanding women's political engagement. Ministries and government officials frequently use platforms like Twitter and Snapchat to communicate policy changes, gather public opinions, and encourage open discussions. Women actively participate in these spaces by sharing their thoughts, organizing campaigns, and promoting discussions on social and political issues. These interactions help build networks of support and create a sense of community among participants, allowing women to influence public debates and amplify their voices. Public figures such as Sara Abdul Rahman Al Sayed, who serves as deputy foreign minister for public diplomacy, demonstrate how women are leveraging these platforms to shape both domestic and international policies.¹⁶

The government's commitment to enhancing political participation is reflected in its development of dedicated e-participation platforms. Platforms like Tafaal, Istitlaa, and Watani offer accessible channels for citizens, including women, youth, and marginalised groups, to submit feedback,

¹⁵ "King Salman appoints Hala Al-Tuwaijri as new Human Rights chief," *Saudi Gazette*, September 22, 2022, <https://www.saudigazette.com.sa/article/625279>

¹⁶ Sara Al Sayed, "Sara Al Sayed," *One Giant Leap*, accessed October 19, 2025, <https://onegiantleap.com/speakers/sara-al-sayed>

propose policies, and engage in consultations.¹⁷ These tools promote inclusive governance by ensuring that diverse voices are heard in decision-making processes.¹⁸ Through participatory budgeting and public consultations, women have the opportunity to influence the allocation of resources and the design of policies that affect their daily lives. The government's approach emphasizes transparency, responsibility, and community-driven problem-solving.

Furthermore, platforms such as Absher and Meras have been instrumental in facilitating direct interaction between the government and citizens.¹⁹ These portals offer women convenient access to government services and allow them to participate in virtual consultations on laws and regulations. By submitting feedback and participating in policy discussions, women can contribute to shaping the governance framework in meaningful ways. Government ministries are also increasingly using online surveys and consultation forums to gather insights, making political participation more accessible and engaging for women across the country.

Overall, women's e-participation in Saudi Arabia is transforming the political landscape by offering new avenues for involvement and representation. These digital initiatives provide a safe and efficient way for women to engage with government processes, advocate for reforms, and influence policies. As part of Vision 2030, the expansion of e-governance tools reflects a broader effort to create a participatory political culture where citizens are empowered to play an active role in shaping their communities and the nation's future. Through these platforms, women's voices are becoming a central part of the Kingdom's governance, fostering greater inclusion and civic engagement.

6. CIVIL SOCIETY AND PUBLIC CONSULTATION

Women's participation in civil society in Saudi Arabia has increased significantly in recent years. This change is part of the Kingdom's broader efforts to promote gender equality and social development, especially under the Vision 2030 reform plan. In Saudi Arabia, types of associations

¹⁷ Saudi Government, "Participation Dashboard," Saudi Government Portal, <https://www.gov.sa/en/participation-dashboard> (accessed October 19, 2024).

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ "Meras, All Your Government Services in One Place," Tools & Solutions, March 25, 2025, <https://tools-solutions-old.cueserve.in/meras-all-your-government-services-in-one-place/#:~:text=The%20Meras%20platform%20is%20an,they%20wish%20to%20have%20issued>
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vary widely and include registered cultural, professional, charitable, socio-political, and reformist groups, as well as informal networks and traditional gatherings. Registered associations such as the Saudi Arabian Society for Culture and Arts operate under government oversight, while many informal groups struggle to gain recognition due to strict regulations.²⁰ Charitable associations, rooted in Islamic practices like zakat, support communities, widows, orphans, and the disabled, though they often face bureaucratic hurdles. Professional associations, such as engineering and medical societies, are licensed but closely monitored, while human rights forums like the National Society for Human Rights operate under government scrutiny. Youth and student groups in universities actively engage in community projects, whereas traditional gatherings (*majalis*) serve as platforms for discussion and petitioning.

Historically, Saudi women's participation in civil society has evolved steadily, beginning with their pioneering efforts in the early 1960s.²¹ In 1962, Saudi women were instrumental in establishing the country's first philanthropic societies, marking the beginning of their organised volunteer work and community service. Motivated by national pride and a sense of responsibility, these women sought to improve the living conditions of Saudi families, especially focusing on childcare, elderly care, health services, education, housing, and support for vulnerable groups. They also included themselves in male organisations. Until 2010, their own registered philanthropic organizations have increased to 30.²² Despite facing challenges such as resource constraints, governmental oversight, and duplication of efforts, women's civil society organisations gradually expanded their scope. In cities like Jeddah and Riyadh, women participate in cultural forums, book clubs, and informal *majalis*, while also joining mixed-gender reformist networks addressing topics such as driving rights, family violence, and entrepreneurship. Groups like Baladi, Naam, and CellA+ focus on political activism and social responsibility, while women also form professional networks, such as the Saudi Professional Women's Network and participate

²⁰ Suad Afif, "Voluntary Work in Civil Society: Saudi Women Volunteers as a Social Capital," *Working Paper No. 10*, International Society for Third-Sector Research, 2010, https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.istr.org/resource/resmgr/working_papers_istanbul/afif_wp10.pdf

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid.

in municipal discussions and volunteer programs.²³ The recent reforms and women's higher education pushed women's role in civil society activities in the kingdom. Women now lead or actively participate in foundations, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and advocacy groups that work on issues such as health, education, and women's rights. Such as the Saudi Women's Rights Group, which advocates for women's legal rights and social freedoms.

The government has also introduced supportive regulations to encourage women's engagement. These include facilitating access to funding, training programs, and digital platforms where women can share ideas, participate in discussions, and collaborate on projects. Moreover, initiatives such as e-participation platforms ensure that women's voices are heard in policymaking and consultations.²⁴ However, women's participation in civil society in Saudi Arabia is a positive development that reflects the country's commitment to empowering women and promoting inclusive growth. By contributing their skills, perspectives, and leadership, women are playing a key role in shaping a more equitable and resilient society.

7. WOMEN AND THE JUDICIARY

In recent years, Saudi Arabia has made significant efforts to increase women's participation in the judiciary as part of broader reforms aimed at enhancing women's rights and economic empowerment. These initiatives are closely aligned with the country's Vision 2030 reform plan, which seeks to create more opportunities for women and integrate them more fully into all sectors of society, including the judicial system.

The judiciary in Saudi Arabia has historically been a male-dominated field, but reforms have been introduced to support women's entry and advancement. As of 2022, around **3782 women had been appointed to roles in the judiciary**, particularly in the Public Prosecution.²⁵ This development marks a notable shift from previous years, reflecting the Kingdom's commitment to

²³ Caroline Montagu, "Civil Society in Saudi Arabia: The Power and Challenges of Association," *Working Paper*, Middle East and North Africa Programme, Chatham House, March 2015, https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/field/field_document/20150331CivilSocietySaudiMontagu.pdf.

²⁴ Digital Government Authority, *E-Participation Controls*, July 31, 2023, <https://dga.gov.sa/en/E-Participation-Controls>

²⁵ Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), *Fifth Periodic Report of Saudi Arabia*, U.N. Doc. CEDAW/C/SAU/5 (March 31, 2022), https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/15/treatybodyexternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=CEDAW%2FC%2FSAU%2F5&Lang=en.

providing women with equal access to professional opportunities and leadership positions within the legal system.¹

Moreover, the number of female lawyers rose from 618 in 2019 to 3,036 in 2022. Additionally, there were 2,833 women training to become lawyers by the end of 2022.²⁶ Women can now also be licensed to perform certain court clerk duties. These women are now actively contributing to legal proceedings and providing essential services in both urban and rural areas. In addition, the Ministry of Justice has developed digital platforms that allow women living in remote areas to access court documents and rulings, thereby improving their ability to seek legal remedies and participate in the judicial process without undue barriers.²⁷ Access to justice has been further supported by amendments to laws and procedures that ensure women are treated equally in marriage, divorce, and other civil matters.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain. The judiciary is still in the process of expanding opportunities for women judges, and their numbers remain small compared to female lawyers. However, seeing the government efforts and policy, it can be said the government may soon appoint women as judge in the Kingdom's courts. Also, the Vision 2030 and the women's department under the Ministry of Justice can more encourage women to join the judicial sector to further support and appointments women in in the judiciary system.

However, women's participation in the judiciary in Saudi Arabia has expanded significantly, it remains an area requiring continued reforms and support. The Kingdom's efforts under Vision 2030 have laid a foundation for progress, but challenges related to legal autonomy, gender balance, and access to justice still need to be addressed to achieve full equality for women in the judiciary. In a society where political avenues are limited, Saudi women also turned to other informal channels to influence public discourse, to advocate the changing process and to influence the government decision-making. The creative activism in journalism, social media platforms, online informal networks (Wasta) and cultural gatherings is becoming a vital space for women to

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ United Nations Office at Geneva, "Experts of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women Praise Saudi Arabia's Efforts to Promote Women's Economic Empowerment, Ask about Progress in Abolishing the Male Guardianship System and Promoting Women's Access to Justice," October 2024, <https://www.ungeneva.org/en/news-media/meeting-summary/2024/10/experts-committee-elimination-discrimination-against-women>

influence the public discourse and change. Thus, these kinds of informal activism are growing in the kingdom and helping women advocating their rights and roles.

Table
Legal and Social Reforms for Women's Empowerment

SL No	Laws	Implemented in	Explanation
1.	Driving	2018	Driving permits for women were officially issued in June 2018
2.	Guardian Law	2019	Saudi Arabia relaxed aspects of the male guardianship system in 2019, allowing women over 21 to travel, work, and access services without a male guardian's approval.
3.	Requirement of wearing the Niqab and Abaya	2023	Under the Vision 2030, Saudi Arabian women are no longer required to wear abayas and niqabs in all activities.
4.	introducing anti-harassment laws		The 2018 Anti-Harassment Law also marked another major milestone for female empowerment, imposing strict penalties—including hefty fines and prison sentences—for workplace harassment.
5.	Saudi Women can join the military	2018	Saudi Arabia opened non-combat military jobs to women in February 2018
6.	Amendment of the Saudi nationality law	2023	On 11 January 2023, King Salman approved an Amendment of the Saudi nationality law that allows Saudi women married to foreign men to pass on Saudi citizenship to their children.
7.	Divorce Law	2019	In January 2019, the Saudi justice ministry approved a new law that would prevent men from secretly divorcing their wives without informing them
8.	Women Space	to 2022	On 22 September 2022, Saudi Arabia announced it would send its first woman into space in early 2023 as part of the Saudi Space Commission's new space program

Source: Author collected from public documents

9. CONCLUSION

Under King Salman, women's involvement in the political sphere of Saudi Arabia has experienced a slow but substantial growth due to a combination of legal, structural, and informal means by which women can be politically active. This has been made evident through the appointment of

women into leadership roles within the Shura Council, the Ministries, the Diplomatic Corps, and various National Authorities, indicating the Government's commitment to establish women in a formal governance role. The progressive reforming of legislation related to Guardianship Law, and allowing freedom of movement for women, has increased the participation of women, in a number of ways, to allow women to be involved in civic and political issues and therefore to have a meaningful role in Policy Development and Decision Making, and to help support the development of their nation. In addition to the formal institutions, women are using various digital platforms, as well as networks established through Civil Society, to create new opportunities for Public Conversation and for them to advocate for Reformation. These two forms of participation also enhance the opportunities available to women for Political Participation within the limits of the existing Electoral and legislative systems. However, the limitations on women's ability to participate in certain areas, especially Foreign Diplomacy and the Judicial, indicate that there are still many barriers that must be overcome in order for women to be fully included in the Political System of Saudi Arabia. The Kingdom's advancements under King Salman demonstrate a methodical and thoughtful approach to women's empowerment, blending symbolic actions with real opportunities in governance and society. To sustain and strengthen women's political participation, continued legal reform, support from institutions, and the development of more informal ways to participate in politics will be necessary to ensure that women's increased visibility leads to actual power and lasting changes in society.